

Program Evaluation and Development of a Nurse Education Module to Improve Psychiatric Patient Agitation/Anxiety Assessment and Care

Rachel Medina, DNP, PMHNP-BC; Glenn Raup, RN, PhD, MBA, MSN, CEN; Taqialdeen Zamil, DNP, PMHNP-BC

Background

- Occupational Safety and Health Administration 2016 workplace violence (WPV) prevention program. "Safety and health training" component was focus of nurse education module
- 2014 California Senate Bill 1299 focused on stricter WPV prevention in healthcare
- 2018 national violence rates in 365 hospitals: 9,436 incidents
- Systematic review of 68 articles showed varying levels of adverse effects on nurses resulting from WPV incidents

1 North	Code Grey	WPV	Battery Report
2017	47	23	25
2018	59	38	21
2019	48	67	23
2 South	Code Grey	WPV	Battery Report
2017	13	1	3
2018	13	26	16
2019	33	23	3

Purpose

Purpose of DNP project was to conduct a two-phase quality improvement project using a programmatic review approach and review of literature to develop a nurse education module and PRN medication protocol that would improve patient agitation/anxiety assessment thereby enhancing milieu safety at a large academic medical center in California

Setting

2 adult inpatient psychiatric units at a large academic medical center in Southern California

Sample

Approximately 28 psychiatric technicians (PT) and registered nurses (RN) on one adult unit. Approximately 20 PT's and RN's on second adult unit

Theoretical Framework

Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Healthcare

Methods

- Obtain IRB approval from CSULA and large academic medical center
 - Phase 1** - Conduct program review, examine violence rates at academic medical center, develop EBP toolkit (nurse education and medication protocol)
 - Phase 2** - Train psychiatric nursing staff to use Clinically Useful Anxiety Outcome Scale & Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale - Excited Component
 - Anonymously survey nursing staff on: demographic data, perception of empowerment, and confidence utilizing assessment tools
 - Train psychiatric physician residents on education module and ordering as needed psychotropics
- EBP protocol recommendations: oral psychotropics include: Haloperidol, Olanzapine, Risperidone and Lorazepam
- Nursing Education Module: Encourage nursing staff to re-assess anxiety / agitation within 30-45 minutes after administration of oral psychotropic. If medication ineffective, nursing staff to page resident on-call and notify

Data Collection

- Phase 1:** Review post project incident report rates of: verbal, physical and sexual abuse; quantity of "code grey" alarms and occurrence of restrictive measures
- Phase 2:** Compare pre and post project nurse perception of empowerment

Actual / Potential Limitations

- Due to time constraints only able to complete phase 1 (topic definition and IRB)
- Residents not on-site at night for new admissions
- Varying level of physician comfort with prescribing PRN benzodiazepines
- Nurse resistance to adoption of new assessment process

Anticipated Findings

- Nurse empowerment will increase after project implementation
- Code grey, assaults against staff, and seclusion / restraints use will decrease after implementation

Recommendations

- Incorporate nurse education module into current practice at facility location
- Modify module as needed
- Continue monitoring IR rates: WPV, code grey alarms, seclusion and restraint use
- Consider adoption on adolescent unit

References

